

Ioana Mohor-Ivan (ed.; coord.)
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In an era when teaching and scholarship are increasingly interdisciplinary, the subject of film studies has come to be recognized as a field in its own right; more than that, it expands and thrives, attracting fresh ideas and research. Although the Film & Literature Studies has been a part of MA curriculum in the Faculty of Letters, Dunarea de Jos University, Galati, Romania, for a little more than two years, a handful of postgraduate students have already come up with a collection of essays under the supervision of Professor Ioana Mohor-Ivan.

The first part of the volume features essays on representations of ancient (Egyptian, Roman-Greek), medieval (Irish, English), and 19th century myths; contributors then examine various heroes and heroines in older or more recent films, some of them with an interdisciplinary approach, analyzing the “journeys” from page to screen; the third part focuses on the influence Gothic fiction has had on contemporary cinema; the volume closes with two essays discussing the opportunities and challenges presented by film posters.

While essay-writing can be intimidating or frustrating, it can be both interesting and achievable, particularly when students are free to choose their topics. The essays in this volume are a case in point. Using elements taken from the humanities (religion, philosophy, history) and the social sciences (sociology, psychology, anthropology), the authors move

casually within rhetorical and literary analyses, building their arguments on secondary and primary source research, ultimately proving they are careful and conscientious readers of other texts. They do go beyond summary and become agents of interpretation, with a good command of inductive and deductive reasoning, which is expected from an academic discourse, alongside proficiency in organization and a proper tone.

For students, essay-writing is an opportunity to grow, to stretch their minds, to develop their original ideas, and to find out what other researchers have written about a topic. Thus, they can see that academic inquiry never stands still and that they can move the boundaries of knowledge in any imaginable direction once they have become active participants in their chosen fields. Above all, the goal of essay-writing is to turn students into better readers, writers and communicators in real-life situations which can be academic, professional, or personal.

Good writing is more a consequence of hard work than genius, and this collection of essays is a solid example of what hard work and enthusiasm from both students and professors can do.